

Havbredey Preliminary Metocean Study

Metocean Preliminary Desk Top Study

Draft Report
Project No 11826846

28 September 2023

Prepared for EUDP IDEA: Integrated Design of Floating Wind Arrays

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Prepared for: EUDP IDEA: Integrated Design of Floating Wind Arrays
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Appendix A DHI Persistence Model (Weather Windows)

Appendix B DHI Extreme Value Analysis (EVA)

Executive Summary

This report presents a preliminary Front-End Engineering Design Metocean Study for the Havbredey Floating Offshore Wind Farm (FOWF) located in Scotland. The results presented herein can only be considered as a pre-FEED study and are aimed to serve as input for preliminary design.

This report is a deliverable of the project Integrated Design for Floating Wind Arrays (IDEA) funded by The Energy Technology and Demonstration Program (EUDP) of the Danish Energy Agency. This deliverable is aligned with the scope of work defined in the International Energy Agency Wind Technology Collaboration (IEA Wind TCP) Task 49 with the same name.

The preliminary metocean study consisted of utilising existing datasets to establish normal and extreme metocean conditions. Analyses of the normal (operational) conditions and extreme conditions were performed at one location close to the lease area representing the Havbredey FOWF, originally called N2 area in the ScotWind leasing round.

DHI provided 20 years (2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31) of time series of hindcast data and analyses of normal and extreme conditions of wind, water levels, currents and waves for one location close to the Havbredey project site.

The present study is suitable for a preliminary (pre-FEED) assessment of the metocean conditions at the site. Additional analyses might be required for a FEED study. Moreover, for detailed design, local metocean measurements and bathymetry survey would be required to establish higher resolution models and more representative and validated conditions.

The preliminary extreme omni-directional values resulting from DHI's analyses at Havbredey project site are summarised in Table 0.1.

Table 0.1 Extreme values table

Extreme values (omni-directional)	Return period [year]		
	1	50	100
Variable			
Wind speed at 10mMSL, 2hr, WS_{10} [m/s]	27.0	36.4	38.0
Wind speed at 150mMSL, 2hr, WS_{150} [m/s]	36.4	49.0	51.2
High water level, WL [mMSL]	2.3	2.7	2.8
Low water level, LWL [mMSL]	-2.2	-2.5	-2.5
Current speed, total, depth-averaged, CS [m/s]	0.8	1.1	1.1
Significant wave height, total, 3hr, H_{m0} [m]	10.8	15.2	15.9
Wave period, T_p [s], associated with significant wave height, H_{m0} [m]	16.0	19.3	19.6
Maximum significant wave height, H_{max} [m]	19.5	27.9	29.3
Maximum wave period, TH_{max} [s], associated with H_{max} [m].	11.4	21.1	22.8
Maximum crest height, C_{max} [m]	12.6	18.2	19.2

1 Introduction

In the context of the Integrated Design for Floating Wind Arrays (IDEA) project funded by The Energy Technology and Demonstration Program (EUDP) of the Danish Energy Agency, this report delivers a preliminary metocean study close to the Havbredey floating offshore wind farm (FOWF) project. This deliverable is aligned with the scope of work defined in the International Energy Agency Wind Technology Collaboration (IEA Wind TCP) Task 49 with the same name.

Figure 1.1 shows the location of all sites awarded within the ScotWind lease round. The site number 14, awarded to Northland Power, represents the currently named Havbredey FOWF project, with a planned installed capacity of 1.5 GW.

The metocean study presented herein utilised 20 years of hindcast datasets available to establish the normal and extreme conditions based on DHI's models and knowledge. Analyses of the normal (operational) and extreme conditions of wind, water levels, currents, and waves at one location close to the Havbredey FOWF site were performed.

Figure 1.1 ScotWind lease areas with awarded developers and planned installed capacity.

Source: [ScotWind leasing round sites and developers | HIE \(offshorewindscotland.org.uk\)](https://www.offshorewindscotland.org.uk)

The long-term normal and extreme metocean conditions had been established based on high-resolution numerical modelling for a period of 20 years from 2001 to 2021 (inclusive). Climate Forecast System (CFSR) Reanalysis winds were used to establish normal conditions. Waves were extracted from DHI's North Europe spectral wave model forced with CFSR (SW_{NE}).

Since this pre-FEED study is relating to a FOWF, the water levels and currents are extracted from DHI's three-dimensional hydrodynamic model available at the region (HD_{UKNS}). Hence, the data delivery can also include time-resolved current profiles.

1.1 Scope of the report

This report is arranged as follows:

- Section 2: provides a description of the atmospheric, spectral wave and hydrodynamic models utilised.
- Section 3: shows the selected analysis point for this study and the list of deliverables.
- Section 4 and 5: present the normal and extreme conditions analyses at the selected analysis point.
- Section 6: provides a summary and recommendations for this study.
- Section 7: lists the references used in this report.
- Appendix A: DHI Persistence Model
- Appendix B: DHI Extreme Value Analysis

2 Data Basis

The data basis for the normal- and extreme analysis is presented in the following section.

For the analysis, the following models have been used to obtain hindcast dataset:

- Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR), NCEP/NOAA
- North_Europe, Wave Parameters (Integrated), MIKE 21 Spectral Wave Model (SW_{NE}), DHI
- UK_and_North_Sea, Ocean, MIKE 3 Hydrodynamic model (HD_{UKNS2}), GFS, DHI

2.1 Climate Forecasting System Reanalysis (CFSR) atmospheric model

Wind data is used for analysis of the wind conditions at the site as well as it is an essential input for forcing the Spectral Wave model (see Section 2.2). This section establishes the wind data via the hindcast data from Climate Forecast System Reanalysis model (CFSR) model.

The Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) atmospheric model was established by the National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP). It was designed as a global, high resolution, coupled atmosphere-ocean-land surface-sea ice system to provide the best estimate of the state of these coupled domains.

CFSR data covers the period from 1979 to 2010 (31 years), and since then, the operational re-forecast dataset, denoted CFSv2, are applied, for which the spatial resolution of some outputs was increased from 0.3° to 0.2° (see Table 2.1) and model configuration was updated. Hereafter, 'CFSR' refers to the combined CFSR and CFSv2 datasets.

Table 2.1 Characteristics of CFSR wind and pressure data

Name	Availability	Temporal sampling	Spatial resolution of 10m wind	Spatial resolution of MSL pressure
CFSR	1979-2010	1 h	0.3 °	0.5 °
CFSRv2	2011-present	1 h	0.2 °	0.5 °

Table 2.2 presents the outputs specifications of CFSR. Based on DHI's experience and local assessments, the CFSR wind is considered representative of approximately 2h averages.

Table 2.2 Output specifications of CFSR (1 h temporal sampling, 0.2° (~23 km) spatial resolution, representative of approximately 2 h averages based on DHI experience)

Parameter	Abbreviation	Unit
Pressure @ mean sea level	P _{MSL}	hPa
Wind speed @ 10 m height	WS10	m/s
Wind direction @ 10 m height	WD10	°N (clockwise from)

The wind data from CFSR are available on an hourly basis from 1979-01-01 to 2023-04-01. For a more consistent analysis, the time period of the dataset used for this assessment was aligned with the available data from the HD_{UKNS} model (2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31) (see more info in Section 2.3). The spatial resolution of the wind data is approximately 0.3° during the full period.

The CFSR parameters utilised for analysis in this assessment are the wind speed [m/s] and wind direction [degree]. More information on CFSR can be found in [Climate Forecast System \(noaa.gov\)](https://www.noaa.gov), [NCAR RDA Dataset ds093.0 \(ucar.edu\)](https://climate.geo.udel.edu/ncar-rda/dataset/ds093.0) and [NCAR RDA Dataset ds094.1 \(ucar.edu\)](https://climate.geo.udel.edu/ncar-rda/dataset/ds094.1).

2.2 North Europe Spectral Wave Model (SW_{NE})

Wave data were established for a 40+ year period through numerical modelling using the MIKE 21 Spectral wave model by DHI (details on MIKE 21 Spectral wave can be found in the general description¹). The wave model was set up with the fully spectral, in-stationary formulation suitable for wave studies involving time-dependent wave events and rapidly-varying wind conditions in space and time and forced by CFSR wind fields. Detailed sensitivity studies of wind forcing, momentum transfer, white-capping, air-sea interaction, etc, were conducted and the results were validated against a large number of in-situ observation across northern Europe as well as satellite altimeter data². The model validation against satellite altimetry measurements at project site is shown as an example in Figure 2.1 The output include integral wave parameters at all grid points and full (2D) wave spectra on a 0.1° grid within the coastal areas.

¹ [MIKE 21 Spectral Waves \(mikepoweredbydhi.com\)](https://www.mikepoweredbydhi.com)

² [MOODv2 Web App \(metocean-on-demand.com\)](https://www.metocean-on-demand.com)

Figure 2.1 Validation of H_{m0} during 1979-2023 against altimetry data at project site. The scatter plot shows a good agreement represented by a low scatter.

The model bathymetry is based on (Bathymetry Consortium EMODnet, 2016). The bathymetry refers to mean sea level (MSL).

The source of bathymetric data used for the model bathymetry is EMODnet. The resulting model bathymetry is shown in Figure 2.2, while the computational mesh is shown in Figure 2.3. The computational element size varies from offshore areas to nearshore areas. The triangular element distance (element centre-to-centre) offshore is approximately 30 km, while the triangular element distance (centre-to-centre) nearshore is down to 3 km. The local site resolution/cell size at N2 is approximately 13 km. All depths in the model bathymetry refer to mean sea level. Special emphasis has been put on having higher resolution elements in areas with offshore wind energy development activity.

The wave data from SW_{NE} are available on an hourly basis from 1979-01-01 to 2021-12-31. For a more consistent analysis, the time period used for this assessment was aligned with the available data from the HD_{UKNS} model (2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31) (see more info in Section 2.3).

The SW_{NE} parameters utilised for analysis in this assessment are the significant wave height [m], peak period [s] and mean wave direction [degree].

Figure 2.2 North Europe Spectral Wave bathymetry from EMODnet for the area of the project site. Depths are relative to Mean Sea Level [MSL] (figure is from MOOD)

Figure 2.3 North Europe Spectral Wave numerical mesh for the area of the project site (figure is from MOOD)

2.3 Hydrodynamic Model (HD_{UKNS})

Water level and 3-dimensional current, salinity and seawater temperature data were established using MIKE 3 Flow model FM by DHI. The model was forced by meteorological GFS model and boundary conditions from a combination of the Copernicus PSY3V3R1 global reanalysis model and the DTU10 satellite derived tidal model. The model was calibrated against water level, current, salinity and temperature observations, and later validated against 43 stations with 1 to 37 recording levels at each station giving a total of 677 recording

levels. A detailed calibration report and a comprehensive validation report are available on MetOcean on Demand (MOOD)³.

The HD_{UKNS} model is based on the modelling software MIKE 3 FM (version 2017) developed by DHI. MIKE 3 FM is based on a flexible mesh approach and it has been developed for applications within oceanographic, coastal and estuarine environments.

The system is based on the numerical solution of the three-dimensional (3D) incompressible Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations invoking the assumptions of Boussinesq and of hydrostatic pressure. Thus the model consists of continuity, momentum, temperature, salinity and density equations and it is closed by a turbulent closure scheme. The free surface is taken into account using a sigma-coordinate transformation approach.

The scientific documentation of MIKE 3 FM is available online⁴.

The HD_{UKNS} model domain covers the waters around the UK and the North Sea as illustrated in Figure 2.4. The model includes coastal sections of Ireland, UK, France, Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Denmark, Sweden and Norway and has three open boundaries towards the North Atlantic and one open boundary in southern Kattegat.

The model bathymetry is based on (Bathymetry Consortium EMODnet, 2016). The bathymetry refers to mean sea level (MSL).

The model resolution (Figure 2.4) varies from 3-6 km in the main part of the model domain to 8-12 km near the three ocean boundaries. The local resolution at project site is approximately 5 km. In a band along the west coast of Netherlands, Germany and Denmark the resolution is as fine as 2-3 km.

³ https://www.metocean-on-demand.com/metadata/waterdata-dataset-UKNS_HD3D_SGEO

⁴ [MIKE 3 Flow Model FM - Hydrodynamic and Transport Module \(mikepoweredbydhi.help\)](#)

Figure 2.4 HD_{UKNS} model bathymetry and mesh

The atmospheric forcing of the HD_{UKNS} model is provided by StormGeo in terms of temporally and spatially varying fields of:

- Wind
- Atmospheric pressure
- Precipitation
- Air temperature
- Cloud cover

The applied atmospheric data is from StormGeo's WRF meteorological model covering the North Atlantic. The data is provided in a resolution of 0.1° x 0.1° in hourly time steps.

In hindcast mode, the HD_{UKNS} model applies 'best-cast' meteorological fields and in forecast mode, it applies forecasted meteorological fields.

The StormGeo data are only available from 2009. Therefore, meteorological fields from Vejr2 of Denmark (0.15°, hourly) were applied in the period 2005-2009 and meteorological fields from Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) (0.3-0.5°, hourly) were applied in the period 2000-2005.

The ocean data from HD_{UKNS} are available on half an hour basis from 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31 extracted from model files. Before analysis, the data were re-sampled from half an hour to an hourly basis.

The HD_{UKNS} parameters utilised for analysis in this assessment are the water level [m], current speed [m/s] and current direction [degree].

3 Analysis Point and Data Delivery

The present section presents a briefly introduction to the analysis point selected for the preliminary metocean study.

3.1 Selection of analysis point

The point selected for the preliminary metocean study is located close to the Havbredey floating offshore wind farm (FOWF) project, approximately 35 km offshore to the northwest of Lewis, UK. The location was chosen along with the project partners to represent a location close to the commercial leased site shown in Section 1. The analysis point will be referred to as N2 herein.

The coordinates for the analysis point N2 are presented in Table 3.1, and is depicted on a map in Figure 3.1.

Table 3.1 Coordinates of point N2

Lon	Lat	Depth	Grid cell size HDUKNS	Grid cell size SWNE
-5.58093°	58.84328°	85.5 m	~ 6 km	~13 km

Figure 3.1 Map indicating the location of point N2 with HDUKNS mesh and bathymetry

3.2 Specification of metocean time series data delivery

Hindcast time series datasets were provided for the following wind, wave and ocean parameters:

- Wind speed at 10 mMSL (WS₁₀)
- Wind speed 150 mMSL (WS₁₅₀) [m/s] (derived from WS₁₀ using power law c.f. Section 4.1)
- Wind direction at 10 mMSL (WD₁₀) [°]
- Significant wave height (H_{m0}) [m]
- Peak wave period (T_p) [s]
- Mean wave direction (MWD) [°]
- Water level (WL) [m]
- Depth averaged current speed (CS) [m/s]
- Current direction (CD) [°]

An overview of the datasets and respective models including information on the spatial - and temporal resolution, and temporal extent, is presented in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Dataset overview

Dataset	Source	Grid cell size	Temporal res.	Temporal extent
Winds	CFSR	~23 km	Hourly	2001-2021
Waves	SW _{NE}	~3-30 km	Hourly	2001-2021
Water level	HD _{UKNS}	~2-12 km	30 min	2001-2021
Depth-averaged	HD _{UKNS}	~2-12 km	30 min	2001-2021
Current profiles	HD _{UKNS}	~2-12 km	30 min	2018

All the time series are delivered in a single file with distinct formats (.mat, .nc, .dfs0 and .xlsx). The total water level (WL) and depth-averaged current speed (CS) and direction (CD) were down sampled to hourly data to match the other variables. The dataset period shared is from 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31 to match the available current and water level datasets.

The wave spectra available from the SW_{NE} model were extracted at the closest point to N2, at 5.5°W 59°N. The hourly data was fitted to obtain the JONSWAP γ parameter at each timestamp. A dataset including this parameter is also part of the digital delivery.

Also, as part of the digital delivery, is one file with one-year period of 3D hourly current data at 88 vertical layers taken directly from the HD_{UKNS} model.

4 Normal Conditions

The present section discusses the normal condition analyses considering wind, waves, water levels and currents, performed at N2.

The analyses were based on the hindcast data obtained by the models: CFSR, SW_{NE} forced with CFSR and HD_{UKNS} for the period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31. The directional analyses were conducted for 12 directional bins of 30 degrees (centred at 0°N, 30°N ...). The normal conditions analyses were conducted for the wind speed (10 mMSL and 150mMSL), water levels (total, tidal and residual), waves and currents. Additionally, exceedance probability, spectral data and weather window analyses, together with misalignments tables as a function of wind speed, monthly-, annual- and directional statistics of the winds were provided.

All the performed analyses results can be found in the digital delivery.

4.1 Winds

The normal wind analysis was carried out at N2 based on the modelled wind data at 10 mMSL above mean sea level (WS_{10}) and hub height at 150 mMSL (WS_{150}) from CFSR for the period 2001-01-01 to 2021-31-12. The wind speed at hub height was derived from WS_{10} mMSL. In summary, the power law (see equation below) with a mean wind shear exponent (α) of 0.14 was used to extrapolate the wind speed (m/s) from 10 mMSL (U_{z1}) to hub height (U_{z2}), where z_1 and z_2 is the height in meters above MSL (IEC, 2019).

$$U_{z2} = U_{z1} \left(\frac{z_2}{z_1} \right)^\alpha$$

Using a shear exponent of 0.14 may result in conservative (high) values at 150m height, but no measurements were available to justify a lower shear, and it is reasonable to assume 0.14 for a pre-FEED level study (IEC, 2019).

Wind direction at hub height (WD_{150}) was assumed to be similar to 10 m above MSL (WD_{10}).

The normal wind conditions discussed in the following sections are presented in terms of:

- Main statistics
- Wind roses
- Weibull parameters
- Workability tables/weather window
- Exceedance

4.1.1 Main Statistics

Time series of wind speed at 10 mMSL and hub height at 150 mMSL are presented in Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2. The maximum wind speeds at 10 mMSL and 150 mMSL are 32.96 m/s and 48.15 m/s, respectively.

Figure 4.1 Time series of wind speed at 10 mMSL (WS_{10}) at N2

Figure 4.2 Time series of wind speed at hub height (WS_{150}) at N2

The monthly statistics of WS_{10} and WS_{150} are presented in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4, and the annual and monthly statistics are summarised in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2. The lowest annual means for WS_{10} and WS_{150} are found in July, 6.9 m/s and 10.1 m/s and the highest annual means are found in January, 33 m/s and 48.2 m/s.

Additionally, the directional statistics for WS_{10} and WS_{150} can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.3 Monthly statistics for 10 mMSL

Table 4.1 Monthly statistics for wind speed at 10 mMSL

(N: number of data points, MEAN: the annual and monthly mean, STD: the annual and monthly standard deviation, MIN: the annual and monthly minimum, P25-75: the annual and monthly 25, 50 and 75 % quantiles, MAX: the annual and monthly maximum).

WS ₁₀	Omni	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
N	184057	15624	14232	15624	15120	15624	15120	15624	15624	15120	15624	15120	15601
MEAN	9.3	11.5	10.9	10.1	8.6	7.6	7.2	6.9	7.5	8.9	10.1	11.1	11.3
STD	4.4	4.9	4.5	4.4	3.8	3.5	3.2	3.2	3.6	4	4.2	4.5	4.9
MIN	0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
P25	6	7.9	7.7	7	5.8	5.1	4.9	4.6	4.9	5.9	7	7.8	7.7
P50	8.9	11.3	10.7	9.8	8.5	7.3	7	6.7	7.2	8.6	10.1	11	11.2
P75	12.2	14.7	14	13.2	11.1	9.9	9.2	9	9.7	11.6	13	14.1	14.5
MAX	33	33	29	32.2	23.4	24.6	21.8	20.4	26.1	27.1	28	27.4	31.6

Figure 4.4 Monthly statistics for 150 mMSL

Table 4.2 Monthly statistics for at 150 mMSL

(N: number of data points, MEAN: the annual and monthly mean, STD: the annual and monthly standard deviation, MIN: the annual and monthly minimum, P25-75: the annual and monthly 25, 50 and 75 % quantiles, MAX: the annual and monthly maximum).

WS ₁₅₀	Omni	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
N	184057	15624	14232	15624	15120	15624	15120	15624	15624	15120	15624	15120	15601
MEAN	13.6	16.8	15.9	14.8	12.6	11.1	10.5	10.1	11	13	14.8	16.2	16.4
STD	6.5	7.1	6.6	6.5	5.6	5.2	4.6	4.7	5.2	5.9	6.2	6.5	7.2
MIN	0	0.2	0.2	0.3	0	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2
P25	8.8	11.5	11.2	10.2	8.4	7.4	7.1	6.7	7.2	8.6	10.2	11.3	11.3
P50	13	16.5	15.7	14.3	12.4	10.7	10.2	9.7	10.5	12.5	14.7	16.1	16.3
P75	17.8	21.5	20.5	19.3	16.1	14.5	13.5	13.1	14.1	17	19	20.6	21.2
MAX	48.2	48.2	42.4	47	34.1	36	31.9	29.9	38.1	39.7	41	40.1	46.2

4.1.2 Wind Roses

The annual wind roses of wind speed 10 and 150 mMSL vs. wind direction at 10 and 150 mMSL with 30° bins are presented in Figure 4.5 and Figure 4.6. The scatter tables are presented in Table 4.3 and Table 4.4.

It is observed that N2 is dominated by south-westerly winds and that the south - and north-easterly winds are less frequent. Given the location of N2 is situated in the belt of global westerly winds, the wind directions were expected to mainly come from south-west.

Figure 4.5 Wind rose – wind speeds at 10 mMSL with an averaging period of 1 hours – 30° bin – directions: coming from N2

Table 4.3 Directional wind frequency of occurrence table for wind speed 10 mMSL and wind direction 10 mMSL

WS10	[-15-15[[15-45[[45-75[[75-105[[105-135[[135-165[[165-195[[195-225[[225-255[[255-285[[285-315[[315-345[Total	Accum
[32-34[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[30-32[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[28-30[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	99.99
[26-28[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.05	99.98
[24-26[0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.15	99.94
[22-24[0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.13	0.07	0.08	0.02	0.01	0.37	99.79
[20-22[0.04	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.27	0.22	0.16	0.06	0.03	0.90	99.42
[18-20[0.09	0.05	0.01	0.03	0.08	0.06	0.16	0.64	0.45	0.36	0.15	0.08	2.13	98.52
[16-18[0.17	0.10	0.05	0.08	0.19	0.13	0.32	1.12	0.97	0.71	0.32	0.18	4.34	96.38
[14-16[0.34	0.18	0.17	0.21	0.40	0.30	0.51	1.69	1.67	0.99	0.42	0.32	7.19	92.05
[12-14[0.59	0.33	0.30	0.46	0.64	0.60	0.83	2.22	2.32	1.40	0.65	0.56	10.89	84.86
[10-12[0.86	0.56	0.49	0.82	1.06	0.84	1.28	2.82	2.41	1.61	0.92	0.79	14.47	73.96
[8-10[1.08	0.82	0.91	1.32	1.49	1.33	1.55	2.76	2.27	1.61	1.14	0.95	17.20	59.50
[6-8[1.07	1.01	1.27	1.57	1.59	1.55	1.63	2.24	1.82	1.50	1.12	1.06	17.41	42.30
[4-6[0.97	0.96	1.16	1.34	1.37	1.37	1.27	1.45	1.31	1.11	0.90	0.91	14.11	24.89
[2-4[0.60	0.59	0.60	0.76	0.74	0.80	0.72	0.68	0.72	0.71	0.63	0.62	8.16	10.78
[0-2[0.20	0.20	0.18	0.22	0.24	0.24	0.21	0.24	0.23	0.24	0.21	0.22	2.62	2.62
Total	6.02	4.83	5.14	6.79	7.82	7.22	8.57	16.32	14.49	10.52	6.55	5.73	100.00	0.00
Accum	6.02	10.85	16.00	22.79	30.61	37.83	46.40	62.71	77.20	87.72	94.27	100.00	0.00	0.00

N2 (5.580929°W; 58.843280°N; d=83.0mMSL)
 Rose plot (2001-01-01–2021-12-31; Δt=1h; T̄=2h) Omni

Figure 4.6 Wind rose – wind speeds at 150 mMSL with an averaging period of 1 hours – 30° bin – directions: coming from N2

Table 4.4 Directional wind frequency of occurrence table for wind speed 150 mMSL and wind direction at 150 mMSL

WS150	[-15-15[[15-45[[45-75[[75-105[[105-135[[135-165[[165-195[[195-225[[225-255[[255-285[[285-315[[315-345[Total	Accum
[48-50[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[46-48[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[44-46[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[42-44[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[40-42[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	99.99
[38-40[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	99.98
[36-38[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.09	99.94
[34-36[0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.17	99.85
[32-34[0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.29	99.68
[30-32[0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.16	0.14	0.09	0.04	0.02	0.54	99.39
[28-30[0.04	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.07	0.30	0.21	0.18	0.07	0.04	0.99	98.85
[26-28[0.08	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.07	0.05	0.14	0.52	0.38	0.30	0.12	0.07	1.82	97.86
[24-26[0.11	0.06	0.03	0.05	0.12	0.08	0.22	0.74	0.65	0.48	0.21	0.13	2.87	96.05
[22-24[0.18	0.11	0.07	0.10	0.21	0.14	0.28	1.03	0.93	0.58	0.27	0.16	4.07	93.17
[20-22[0.27	0.14	0.15	0.20	0.32	0.28	0.40	1.25	1.31	0.77	0.33	0.27	5.69	89.11
[18-20[0.40	0.24	0.20	0.29	0.44	0.39	0.58	1.52	1.60	0.96	0.43	0.38	7.43	83.42
[16-18[0.54	0.33	0.27	0.50	0.64	0.50	0.76	1.83	1.63	1.06	0.59	0.48	9.12	75.99
[14-16[0.67	0.45	0.44	0.64	0.85	0.71	0.98	1.95	1.66	1.15	0.71	0.59	10.79	66.87
[12-14[0.74	0.56	0.62	0.94	1.02	0.91	1.09	1.88	1.54	1.11	0.76	0.65	11.79	56.08
[10-12[0.73	0.70	0.86	1.06	1.10	1.06	1.09	1.72	1.36	1.04	0.82	0.74	12.28	44.29
[8-10[0.73	0.67	0.86	1.08	1.03	1.06	1.08	1.28	1.09	0.94	0.69	0.72	11.22	32.01
[6-8[0.65	0.66	0.79	0.87	0.93	0.90	0.83	0.95	0.87	0.73	0.60	0.60	9.36	20.79
[4-6[0.49	0.47	0.50	0.59	0.61	0.66	0.57	0.56	0.58	0.58	0.48	0.47	6.55	11.43
[2-4[0.26	0.26	0.25	0.34	0.33	0.35	0.31	0.30	0.32	0.33	0.30	0.29	3.64	4.88
[0-2[0.10	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.09	0.11	1.24	1.24
Total	6.02	4.83	5.14	6.79	7.82	7.22	8.57	16.32	14.49	10.52	6.55	5.73	100.00	0.00
Accum	6.02	10.85	16.00	22.79	30.61	37.83	46.40	62.71	77.20	87.72	94.27	100.00	0.00	0.00

4.1.3 Weibull Parameters

Weibull parameters for normal wind speeds have been calculated for the omni-directional conditions for WS₁₀ and WS₁₅₀. The Weibull scale (A) and shape (k) parameters fitted to the omni-directional wind data and the corresponding histograms are shown in Figure 4.7 and Figure 4.8.

Additionally, the following Weibull parameters for WS₁₀ and WS₁₅₀ can be found in a table in the digital delivery: mean [m/s], scale (A) [m/s], shape (k) [-] and frequency (f) [-].

Figure 4.7 Histogram and Weibull fit parameters for wind speed 10 mSL at N2

Figure 4.8 Histogram and Weibull fit parameters for wind speed 150 mSL at N2

4.1.4 Workability table/ Weather window

A weather window is defined as a continued occurrence during which the given conditions (duration and threshold) are fulfilled. Weather windows of WS_{10} and WS_{150} were calculated for duration of 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60 and 72 hours and for wind speed threshold of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 m/s. Analyses were performed for the 20-, 50- and 80-percentiles values.

The results of the analyses at N2 are presented in graphical and tabular format and they illustrate the percentage of time during which a given condition can be

expected to occur in each month. The vertical bars in the plot indicate the standard deviation for each threshold, which are also designated by the numbers in the parentheses. A more in-depth explanation of the weather windows can be found in the DHI Persistence (Weather Windows) document in Appendix A.

Figure 4.9 and Table 4.5 present the weather window of WS_{10} for an operability window of 2 hours and 50-percentile. The weather window of WS_{10} is lower during winter (November to January) and higher during summer (May to August). As an example, for May month there is a ~60% chance that the wind speed will be lower than 8 m/s for a window of 2 hours (50-percentile).

All the performed weather windows of WS_{10} and WS_{150} can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.9 Persistence (weather-window) of wind speed 10 mMSL at N2 for several thresholds. Window of 2 hours (50-percentile).

Table 4.5 Frequency table of persistence (weather-window) of wind speed 10 mMSL at N2 for several thresholds. Window duration of 2 hours (50-percentile)

WS_{10} [m/s]	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
< 2	0.7	0.8	1.4	2.3	3.2	3	3.6	3.5	2.2	1.1	1	1.2
< 4	3.2	5.3	6.8	11.5	14.7	15.9	17.3	14.3	10.6	6.5	4.7	5
< 6	10.7	13.2	16.2	26.4	35.8	36.2	40.3	31.3	25.9	16.5	14.3	12.1
< 8	25.1	27.5	31.7	45.6	58.1	62.8	64.8	57.4	43.7	31.4	26.3	24.5
< 10	37.4	45.4	49.2	64.7	75.4	81.5	81.5	75.3	61.2	50.9	42.2	40
< 12	55	62.7	67.7	81.3	89.3	93.5	93.5	88.8	76	67.5	58.3	58
< 14	69.1	75.4	79.6	92	96.1	98.5	98.1	95.5	88.3	84.1	74.6	71.4

4.1.5 Exceedance

Directional exceedance analysis was performed for WS_{10} and WS_{150} at N2, and the results are presented in Figure 4.10 and Figure 4.11. The directional exceedance analysis depicts that the highest exceedance values occurred in the South-west sector and the lowest exceedance values in the south – and north-east sectors. Overall, the omni-annual wind speed at 10 mMSL of 29 m/s and wind speed at 150 mMSL of 42 m/s are exceeded approximately 1 hour per year at N2. Corresponding directional wind speed exceedance tables are presented in Table 4.6 and Table 4.7.

Additionally, the monthly and annual exceedance for WS_{10} and WS_{150} can be found in digital delivery.

Figure 4.10 30-degree directional bin wind speed at 10 mMSL exceedance at N2

Table 4.6 Summary table of 30-degree directional bin wind speed at 10 mMSL exceedance at N2

N2 (5.580929°W; 58.843280°N; d=83.0mMSL)
 Exceedance (2001-01-01-2021-12-31; Δt=1h; T=2h) CFSR - Directional

Exceedance [%]

	Omni	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330
0	100.000	6.021	4.833	5.142	6.793	7.817	7.224	8.565	16.316	14.490	10.517	6.546	5.734
2	97.381	5.822	4.637	4.965	6.575	7.578	6.984	8.353	16.080	14.256	10.278	6.340	5.515
4	89.218	5.224	4.043	4.361	5.819	6.836	6.189	7.634	15.397	13.541	9.566	5.711	4.898
6	75.109	4.257	3.081	3.198	4.480	5.468	4.822	6.368	13.944	12.231	8.458	4.815	3.987
8	57.704	3.191	2.069	1.928	2.915	3.878	3.277	4.741	11.707	10.411	6.958	3.700	2.929
10	40.504	2.111	1.250	1.023	1.601	2.391	1.943	3.189	8.952	8.144	5.351	2.566	1.983
12	26.039	1.250	0.686	0.535	0.776	1.327	1.105	1.910	6.136	5.730	3.745	1.647	1.192
14	15.145	0.658	0.352	0.239	0.319	0.686	0.509	1.080	3.912	3.414	2.344	0.997	0.636
16	7.952	0.323	0.170	0.073	0.108	0.283	0.213	0.573	2.220	1.748	1.351	0.573	0.317
18	3.616	0.150	0.066	0.020	0.028	0.097	0.080	0.257	1.103	0.783	0.644	0.254	0.133
20	1.482	0.064	0.017	0.010	0.001	0.021	0.024	0.101	0.468	0.330	0.286	0.108	0.052
22	0.590	0.021	0.007	0.007	-	0.004	0.002	0.038	0.198	0.112	0.126	0.042	0.022
24	0.215	0.007	0.003	0.002	-	-	0.001	0.014	0.070	0.043	0.048	0.020	0.008
26	0.063	0.001	0.002	-	-	-	-	0.004	0.017	0.015	0.015	0.007	0.003
28	0.018	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.008	0.001	0.001
30	0.006	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	0.001	0.002	-	0.003	-	0.001
32	0.002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.002	-	-
34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 4.11 30-degree directional bin wind speed at 150 mMSL exceedance at N2

Table 4.7 Summary table of 30-degree directional bin wind speed at 150 mMSL exceedance at N2

N2 (5.580929°W; 58.843280°N; d=83.0mMSL)
Exceedance (2001-01-01-2021-12-31; Δt=1h; T=2h) CFSR - Directional

WS ₁₅₀ [m/s] ≥	Exceedance [%]												
	Omni	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330
0	100.000	6.021	4.833	5.142	6.793	7.817	7.224	8.565	16.316	14.490	10.517	6.546	5.734
2	98.763	5.926	4.731	5.055	6.688	7.705	7.115	8.458	16.199	14.381	10.422	6.458	5.625
4	95.122	5.663	4.468	4.804	6.351	7.375	6.770	8.152	15.900	14.064	10.088	6.154	5.333
6	88.571	5.176	3.997	4.308	5.762	6.764	6.113	7.580	15.342	13.485	9.511	5.674	4.859
8	79.210	4.528	3.336	3.522	4.896	5.832	5.218	6.747	14.397	12.618	8.780	5.077	4.257
10	67.992	3.802	2.663	2.652	3.812	4.807	4.160	5.666	13.113	11.533	7.845	4.387	3.542
12	55.712	3.071	1.965	1.804	2.748	3.705	3.096	4.578	11.393	10.173	6.801	3.571	2.807
14	43.919	2.337	1.403	1.188	1.811	2.689	2.185	3.493	9.512	8.634	5.691	2.813	2.162
16	33.131	1.671	0.957	0.747	1.167	1.843	1.478	2.510	7.564	6.971	4.545	2.103	1.575
18	24.007	1.127	0.625	0.475	0.669	1.207	0.980	1.754	5.735	5.339	3.490	1.515	1.090
20	16.578	0.729	0.382	0.277	0.375	0.763	0.588	1.176	4.217	3.743	2.530	1.087	0.711
22	10.891	0.460	0.246	0.127	0.180	0.441	0.308	0.776	2.965	2.431	1.762	0.759	0.437
24	6.826	0.281	0.134	0.055	0.082	0.230	0.173	0.498	1.936	1.497	1.181	0.486	0.273
26	3.953	0.169	0.071	0.021	0.032	0.112	0.092	0.283	1.196	0.852	0.698	0.280	0.147
28	2.136	0.087	0.029	0.013	0.004	0.040	0.043	0.146	0.675	0.468	0.396	0.156	0.078
30	1.147	0.046	0.012	0.009	-	0.015	0.014	0.080	0.371	0.260	0.221	0.084	0.036
32	0.609	0.022	0.007	0.008	-	0.005	0.003	0.039	0.208	0.120	0.131	0.045	0.022
34	0.318	0.011	0.003	0.002	-	0.001	0.001	0.024	0.108	0.060	0.074	0.023	0.012
36	0.153	0.005	0.002	0.001	-	-	-	0.010	0.048	0.033	0.035	0.015	0.004
38	0.062	0.001	0.002	-	-	-	-	0.004	0.017	0.014	0.015	0.007	0.003
40	0.023	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	0.002	0.003	0.005	0.009	0.002	0.002
42	0.010	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.004	-	0.001
44	0.005	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	0.001	0.001	-	0.002	-	0.001
46	0.003	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.001	-	0.002	-	-
48	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.001	-	-
50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

4.2 Water Levels

The normal water level analysis was carried out at N2 based on the modelled total water levels data from HD_{UKNS} model for the period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

The normal water level conditions discussed in the following sections are presented in terms of:

- Astronomical water levels and Main statistics
- Exceedance

4.2.1 Astronomical Water Levels and Main Statistics

The modelled total water levels (WL_{Total}) underwent a tidal harmonic analysis to separate the tidal and the non-tidal (residual) components. The 'de-tiding' operation was conducted using the U-tide toolbox⁵.

The water level time series of total (black), tidal (blue) and residual (green) components are shown in Figure 4.12, while the statistics of the dataset are summarised in Table 4.8. The predicted maximum and minimum total water levels are 2.64 and -2.49 m, respectively.

Additionally, the monthly statistics and time series for WL_{Total}, WL_{Tide}, and WL_{Residual} can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.12 Time series of WL_{Total}, WL_{Tide}, and WL_{Residual} at N2

Table 4.8 Statistics of water levels at N2

	MEAN	MIN	MAX	STD
WL _{Total}	0	-2.49	2.64	0.94
WL _{Residual}	0	-0.52	1.13	0.19
WL _{Tidal}	0	-2.14	2.08	0.93

⁵ Codiga, Daniel. (2011). Unified tidal analysis and prediction using the UTide Matlab functions. 10.13140/RG.2.1.3761.2008.

The astronomical values of water levels at N2 for MSL are presented in Table 4.9, which comprises of:

- HSWL: highest still WL
- HAT: maximum predicted
- MSL: mean predicted WL
- LAT: minimum predicted WL
- LSWL: Lowest still WL

The water levels at N2 are semi-diurnal with two high and two low tides per day with a tidal range (HAT-LAT) of 5.13 m. The presented tidal analysis does not account for local water level changes due to climate change and vertical land movements.

Table 4.9 Characteristic astronomical values of water level at N2.

Point	Units	HSWL	HAT	MSL	LAT	LSWL
N2	mMSL	2.64	2.08	0	-2.14	-2.49

4.2.2

4.2.3 Exceedance

Directional exceedance analysis was performed for total water level at N2, and the results are presented in Figure 4.13. The directional exceedance analysis depicts that the highest exceedance values occurred in the western sector.

Corresponding directional wind speed exceedance tables are presented in Table 4.10.

Additionally, the monthly exceedance for the total water level can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.13 30-degree directional bin WL exceedance at N2

Table 4.10 Summary table of 30-degree directional bin WL exceedance at N2

N2 (5.580929°W; 58.843280°N; d=83.0mMSL)
 Exceedance (2001-01-01–2021-12-31; Δt=1h; T̄=3h) HD_{UKNS} - Directional

		Exceedance [%]												
		Omni	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330
WL _{Total} [mMSL] >	-2.5	100.000	11.140	6.385	2.732	2.554	1.414	0.805	0.834	3.484	17.644	30.569	12.877	9.582
	-2.25	99.989	11.135	6.385	2.732	2.554	1.414	0.805	0.834	3.484	17.644	30.566	12.876	9.581
	-2	99.708	11.076	6.369	2.725	2.546	1.412	0.805	0.834	3.480	17.619	30.483	12.838	9.521
	-1.75	98.396	10.855	6.257	2.686	2.512	1.397	0.799	0.830	3.463	17.461	30.113	12.649	9.373
	-1.5	95.093	10.404	6.011	2.576	2.431	1.360	0.786	0.812	3.405	17.043	29.148	12.159	8.959
	-1.25	89.475	9.694	5.591	2.420	2.290	1.295	0.747	0.779	3.286	16.190	27.491	11.364	8.328
	-1	82.241	8.824	5.080	2.207	2.107	1.191	0.693	0.716	3.063	15.025	25.324	10.433	7.579
	-0.75	74.000	7.875	4.508	1.986	1.917	1.074	0.618	0.654	2.782	13.640	22.812	9.344	6.792
	-0.5	65.580	6.960	3.955	1.760	1.714	0.948	0.548	0.580	2.492	12.165	20.187	8.248	6.002
	-0.25	57.839	6.123	3.485	1.563	1.497	0.827	0.480	0.511	2.206	10.761	17.812	7.281	5.292
	0	50.445	5.304	3.033	1.359	1.305	0.722	0.426	0.440	1.945	9.435	15.552	6.296	4.627
	0.25	43.010	4.467	2.536	1.162	1.118	0.618	0.371	0.377	1.692	8.167	13.290	5.303	3.907
	0.5	34.819	3.515	1.991	0.942	0.915	0.487	0.306	0.311	1.432	6.782	10.799	4.234	3.106
	0.75	25.811	2.483	1.431	0.693	0.670	0.375	0.230	0.237	1.142	5.197	8.064	3.065	2.224
	1	17.178	1.535	0.800	0.458	0.465	0.257	0.158	0.165	0.798	3.595	5.412	1.985	1.451
	1.25	9.994	0.832	0.494	0.270	0.277	0.142	0.099	0.104	0.511	2.174	3.230	1.083	0.780
1.5	4.610	0.318	0.208	0.111	0.129	0.059	0.044	0.058	0.274	1.081	1.566	0.449	0.312	
1.75	1.510	0.076	0.051	0.035	0.041	0.020	0.015	0.024	0.115	0.409	0.526	0.118	0.079	
2	0.284	0.010	0.006	0.004	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.006	0.030	0.088	0.106	0.015	0.005	
2.25	0.030	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.001	0.003	0.012	0.012	0.001	-	
2.5	0.003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.002	0.001	-	-	
2.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

4.3 Currents

The normal current analysis was carried out at N2 based on the modelled total depth-averaged hydrodynamic data from HD_{UKNS} model for the period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

The normal current conditions discussed in the following sections are presented in terms of:

- Main statistics
- Current roses
- Current profiles

4.3.1 Main Statistics

Time series of depth averaged current speed is presented in Figure 4.14. The maximum current speed is 1.05 m/s.

Figure 4.14 Time series of current speed at N2

The monthly statistics of CS are presented in Figure 4.15, and the annual and monthly statistics are summarised in

Table 4.11. The lowest annual means for CS are found in May to July, 0.22 m/s and the highest annual means are found in November and January, 0.24 m/s. Additionally, the directional statistics for CS can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.15 Monthly statistics of current speed at N2

Table 4.11 Annual and monthly statistics for current speed

(N: number of data points, MEAN: the annual and monthly mean, STD: the annual and monthly standard deviation, MIN: the annual and monthly minimum, P25-75: the annual and monthly 25, 50 and 75 % quantiles, MAX: the annual and monthly maximum).

CS _{Total}	Omni	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
N	184057	15624	14232	15624	15120	15624	15120	15624	15624	15120	15624	15120	15601
MEAN	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.23
STD	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13
MIN	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
P25	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
P50	0.22	0.22	0.21	0.22	0.21	0.22	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22
P75	0.31	0.33	0.32	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.3	0.3	0.31	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32
MAX	1.05	1.05	0.91	0.91	0.69	0.73	0.64	0.58	0.77	0.73	0.84	0.82	0.83

4.3.2 Current Roses

The annual current rose for CS at N2 with respect to CD for 30° bin is presented in Figure 4.16.

The current rose indicates that the currents are mainly going to the north-east.

Figure 4.16 Current rose – current speeds with 30° bin – directions: coming from N2

4.3.3 Current Profiles

Current profiles for N2 are obtained by the HD_{UKNS} model for year 2018 for the 5th, 25th, 50th, 75th and 95th quantiles and the mean, which is presented in Figure 4.17. The mean current speed is relatively constant throughout the water column ranging between 0.18 m/s at the bottom to 0.3 m/s at the surface (relative steep slope), indicating that the currents are predominantly driven by the tides and less by the winds.

The time series of current profiles shown below are available in the digital delivery. Also, standard power law profiles can be used to derive near-seabed and near-surface currents from the depth-averaged values (not shown).

Figure 4.17 Current profiles (5th, 25th, 50th, 75th and 95th quantiles and the mean) from HD_{UKNS} at N2

4.4 Waves

The normal wave analysis was carried out at N2 based on the modelled total wave data from SW_{NE} model forced with CFSR for the period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

The normal wave conditions discussed in the following sections are presented in terms of:

- Main statistics
- Wave roses
- Exceedance
- Scatter diagrams
- Wind-wave misalignment

- Workability tables/Weather window

4.4.1 Main Statistics

Time series of significant wave height (H_{m0}) at N2 are shown in Figure 4.18. The maximum predicted significant wave is 14.33 m.

Figure 4.18 Time series of H_{m0} at N2

The monthly statistics of H_{m0} are presented in Figure 4.19, and the annual and monthly statistics are summarised in Table 4.12. The lowest annual mean H_{m0} are found in July, 1.5 m, and the highest annual mean are found in January, 3.8 m.

Additionally, the directional statistics of H_{m0} can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.19 Monthly statistics for H_{m0} at N2

Table 4.12 Monthly statistics for H_{m0}

(N: number of data points, MEAN: the annual and monthly mean, STD: the annual and monthly standard deviation, MIN: the annual and monthly minimum, P25-75: the annual and monthly 25, 50 and 75 % quantiles, MAX: the annual and monthly maximum).

H_{m0}	Omni	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
N	184057	15624	14232	15624	15120	15624	15120	15624	15624	15120	15624	15120	15601
MEAN	2.6	3.8	3.6	3.2	2.4	1.9	1.6	1.5	1.7	2.3	2.8	3.4	3.6
STD	1.5	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.1	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.8	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.7
MIN	0.3	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.6
P25	1	1.8	1.6	1.4	1.2	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.8	1	1.1	1.6	1.4
P50	2.3	3.4	3.2	2.8	2.2	1.7	1.5	1.4	1.5	2.1	2.5	3.1	3.3
P75	5.6	7.2	6.6	5.9	4.6	3.6	2.9	2.8	3.3	4.4	5.3	6.2	6.9
MAX	14.3	14.3	14.1	13.2	9	9.5	6.9	5.9	8.2	9.4	9.9	10.5	12.9

4.4.2 Wave Roses

The wave rose for H_{m0} at N2 with respect to mean wave direction (MWD) for 30° bin is presented in Figure 4.20.

The wave rose indicate that the waves are mainly coming from the west, which is a shift to the right compared to the predominant wind direction coming mainly from south-west.

Figure 4.20 Wave rose – H_{m0} – 30° bin – directions: coming from N2

Table 4.13 Directional wave frequency of occurrence table for H_{m0} and MWD

Hm0	[-15-15[[15-45[[45-75[[75-105[[105-135[[135-165[[165-195[[195-225[[225-255[[255-285[[285-315[[315-345[Total	Accum
[14-15[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[13-14[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[12-13[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.02	99.99
[11-12[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.05	99.98
[10-11[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.07	99.93
[9-10[0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.12	0.02	0.01	0.17	99.86
[8-9[0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.28	0.06	0.03	0.44	99.69
[7-8[0.07	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.11	0.52	0.12	0.05	0.90	99.25
[6-7[0.16	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.31	0.92	0.29	0.11	1.88	98.34
[5-6[0.30	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.87	1.85	0.59	0.24	4.02	96.47
[4-5[0.73	0.19	0.04	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.30	1.88	3.27	1.16	0.66	8.32	92.44
[3-4[1.66	0.58	0.21	0.27	0.13	0.07	0.10	0.63	3.34	5.54	2.08	1.40	16.00	84.13
[2-3[3.35	1.69	0.68	0.63	0.52	0.27	0.26	1.09	4.93	8.04	3.49	2.81	27.75	68.13
[1-2[4.27	3.29	1.51	1.34	0.64	0.39	0.39	1.12	5.38	8.68	4.33	3.58	34.90	40.38
[0-1[0.57	0.54	0.27	0.26	0.12	0.06	0.07	0.17	0.76	1.26	0.74	0.67	5.48	5.48
Total	11.14	6.39	2.73	2.55	1.41	0.81	0.83	3.48	17.64	30.57	12.88	9.56	100.00	0.00
Accum	11.14	17.53	20.26	22.81	24.23	25.03	25.86	29.35	46.99	77.56	90.44	100.00	0.00	0.00

4.4.3 Exceedance

Directional exceedance analysis was performed for H_{m0} at N2, and the results are presented in Figure 4.21. The directional exceedance analysis depicts that the highest exceedance values occurred in the western sector and the lowest exceedance values in the south and south-east sectors. Overall, the omni-annual H_{m0} of 12.5 m are exceeded approximately 1 hour per year at N2. Corresponding directional H_{m0} exceedance tables are presented in Table 4.14.

Additionally, the monthly exceedance for H_{m0} can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.21 30-degree directional bin H_{m0} exceedance at N2

Table 4.14 Summary table of 30-degree directional bin H_{m0} exceedance at N2

N2 (5.580929°W; 58.843280°N; d=83.0mMSL)
Exceedance (2001-01-01-2021-12-31; $\Delta t=1h$; $T=3h$) SW_{NE} - Directional

		Exceedance [%]												
		Omni	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330
$H_{m0, Total} [m] \geq$	0	100.000	11.140	6.385	2.732	2.554	1.414	0.805	0.834	3.484	17.644	30.569	12.877	9.562
	1	94.520	10.571	5.844	2.464	2.298	1.299	0.741	0.764	3.310	16.886	29.312	12.142	8.691
	2	59.621	6.303	2.554	0.955	0.961	0.663	0.347	0.379	2.194	11.505	20.634	7.812	5.315
	3	31.872	2.955	0.861	0.272	0.336	0.146	0.079	0.117	1.108	6.573	12.592	4.324	2.509
	4	15.871	1.298	0.281	0.058	0.070	0.016	0.008	0.015	0.484	3.234	7.051	2.248	1.109
	5	7.556	0.569	0.084	0.020	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.180	1.358	3.781	1.092	0.453
	6	3.535	0.265	0.041	0.011	0.002	-	0.001	-	0.083	0.484	1.934	0.505	0.210
	7	1.656	0.109	0.012	0.005	-	-	-	-	0.025	0.179	1.014	0.212	0.098
	8	0.755	0.043	0.001	-	-	-	-	-	0.003	0.066	0.498	0.097	0.046
	9	0.310	0.016	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.001	0.022	0.217	0.040	0.014
	10	0.142	0.007	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.009	0.102	0.018	0.008
	11	0.071	0.003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.002	0.054	0.008	0.004
	12	0.025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.022	0.003	0.001
	13	0.006	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.005	0.001	-
	14	0.002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.002	-	-
	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

4.4.4 Scatter Diagrams

Analyses of joint occurrences at N2 have been carried out for the following:

- Significant wave height and peak wave period
- Significant wave height and wind speed at 150 m

Scatter diagram of the omni-directional significant wave height and peak wave period (H_{m0} vs. T_p) at N2 for total sea-state is shown in Figure 4.22.

From the scatter plot of total H_{m0} vs. T_p , the wave climate is a combination of short-period waves – generated by local winds – and long-period waves (swell). The peak wave periods for the larger local wind-waves are mostly within 20 s and the significant wave height goes up to 14.2 m. The corresponding scatter table is shown in Table 4.15.

Scatter diagram of the omni-directional total significant wave height and wind speed at hub height (H_{m0} vs. WS_{150}) at N2 is shown in Figure 4.23.

From the scatter plot of total H_{m0} vs. WS_{150} , the relation between total H_{m0} and WS_{150} shows a tendency for the largest waves to occur during strong wind speed condition. The corresponding scatter table is shown in Table 4.16.

Additionally, the scatter diagram of the omni-directional total significant wave height and wind speed at 10 mMSL (H_{m0} vs. WS_{10}), and corresponding scatter table can be found in the digital delivery.

Figure 4.22 Scatter diagram of total H_{m0} and T_p at N2

Table 4.15 Scatter table of total H_{m0} and T_p at N2

H_{m0}/T_p	[0-1[[1-2[[2-3[[3-4[[4-5[[5-6[[6-7[[7-8[[8-9[[9-10[[10-11[[11-12[[12-13[[13-14[[14-15[Total	Accum
[28.5-30[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[27-28.5[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[25.5-27[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[24-25.5[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[22.5-24[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[21-22.5[0.00	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	99.99
[19.5-21[0.00	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.16	99.93
[18-19.5[0.00	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.49	99.76
[16.5-18[0.00	0.15	0.19	0.22	0.25	0.21	0.11	0.10	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.32	99.27
[15-16.5[0.01	0.29	0.58	0.81	0.69	0.55	0.37	0.21	0.15	0.07	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	3.78	97.95
[13.5-15[0.03	0.76	2.03	2.65	1.83	1.04	0.47	0.28	0.16	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.32	94.17
[12-13.5[0.11	1.97	4.64	3.92	2.14	0.91	0.51	0.20	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	14.46	84.84
[10.5-12[0.34	6.47	8.86	3.98	1.81	0.88	0.28	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	22.67	70.39
[9-10.5[1.31	12.52	5.86	2.10	0.90	0.24	0.10	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	23.06	47.72
[7.5-9[2.04	7.15	2.63	1.63	0.60	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	14.16	24.66
[6-7.5[1.12	2.72	2.52	0.55	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.94	10.51
[4.5-6[0.30	2.53	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.16	3.57
[3-4.5[0.22	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.41	0.41
[1.5-3[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
[0-1.5[0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	5.48	34.90	27.75	16.00	8.32	4.02	1.88	0.90	0.44	0.17	0.07	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00
Accum	5.48	40.38	68.13	84.13	92.44	96.47	98.34	99.25	99.69	99.86	99.93	99.98	99.99	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00

Figure 4.23 Scatter diagram of total H_{m0} and WS_{150} wind speed at N2

Table 4.16 Scatter table of total H_{m0} and WS_{150} at N2

Hm0/ WS150	[0-1]	[1-2]	[2-3]	[3-4]	[4-5]	[5-6]	[6-7]	[7-8]	[8-9]	[9-10]	[10-11]	[11-12]	[12-13]	[13-14]	[14-15]	Total	Accum
[48-50]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[46-48]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[44-46]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[42-44]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
[40-42]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	99.99
[38-40]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	99.98
[36-38]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.09	99.94
[34-36]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17	99.85
[32-34]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.29	99.68
[30-32]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.09	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.54	99.39
[28-30]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.19	0.27	0.19	0.14	0.10	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.99	98.85
[26-28]	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.23	0.46	0.47	0.33	0.21	0.08	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.82	97.86
[24-26]	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.60	0.88	0.67	0.39	0.18	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.87	96.05
[22-24]	0.00	0.00	0.41	1.27	1.23	0.73	0.31	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.07	93.17
[20-22]	0.00	0.04	1.21	2.06	1.48	0.64	0.22	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.69	89.11
[18-20]	0.00	0.29	2.63	2.66	1.32	0.42	0.11	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.43	83.42
[16-18]	0.00	1.20	4.13	2.54	0.93	0.26	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.12	75.99
[14-16]	0.01	2.86	4.88	2.18	0.68	0.15	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.79	66.87
[12-14]	0.10	5.29	4.39	1.51	0.40	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.79	56.08
[10-12]	0.39	6.82	3.63	1.12	0.27	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	12.28	44.29
[8-10]	1.11	6.59	2.60	0.73	0.15	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.22	32.01
[6-8]	1.45	5.49	1.81	0.48	0.11	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.36	20.79
[4-6]	1.28	3.73	1.15	0.31	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.55	11.43
[2-4]	0.83	1.98	0.60	0.19	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.64	4.88
[0-2]	0.32	0.63	0.20	0.07	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.24	1.24
Total	5.48	34.90	27.75	16.00	8.32	4.02	1.88	0.90	0.44	0.17	0.07	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00
Accum	5.48	40.38	68.13	84.13	92.44	96.47	98.34	99.25	99.69	99.86	99.93	99.98	99.99	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00

4.4.5 Wind-wave misalignment

The wind-wave misalignment was defined as the wind direction minus the MWD for each model time step and was analysed with respect to the wind speed at 10 and 150 mMSL. For example, if the wind is coming from south ($WD = 180^\circ N$) and the mean wave direction is from east ($MWD = 270^\circ N$), then the misalignment angle is $-90^\circ N$.

The wind-wave misalignment analysis was performed for both wind conditions at WS_{10} and WS_{150} . The results for WS_{10} are presented in this report and the results for WS_{150} can be found in the digital delivery folder.

Scatter diagrams of the misalignment against WS_{10} at N2 are presented in Figure 4.24, with the associated scatter table presented in Table 4.17. The

frequency distribution for WD_{10} is presented in Figure 4.25, with the associated frequency distribution table presented in Table 4.18.

The analysis shows misalignments above 30° for the lower values of wind speed, and as expected, the misalignment is reduced for larger values of wind speed, where the wind sea part dominates.

The probability frequency analyses of misalignment show that for WD_{10} from 240° (orange curve) there is a 60% occurrence of 30° misalignment.

Figure 4.24 Scatter diagram of wind-wave misalignment vs. WS_{10} and WD_{10} at N2. The coloured lines show the average misalignment for each WD sector

Table 4.17 Scatter table of wind-wave misalignment vs. WS_{10} and WD at N2

N2 (5.580929°W; 58.843280°N; d=83.0mMSL)
CFSR WD_{10} , SW_{NE} , MWD_{Total} (2001-01-01-2021-12-31; $\Delta t=1h$; $\bar{T}=2h$) by WD_{10}

		WS_{10} (m/s)																
		[0-2[[2-4[[4-6[[6-8[[8-10[[10-12[[12-14[[14-16[[16-18[[18-20[[20-22[[22-24[[24-26[[26-28[[28-30[[30-32[[32-34[
WD_{10} (°N-from)	All	5.36	8.51	10.38	13.04	17.07	17.67	16.21	15.79	14.84	14.14	13.30	11.77	9.56	8.75	2.00	8.37	-1.15
	[-15-15[-49.98	-36.87	-26.01	-12.81	-7.59	-7.57	-6.45	-3.75	-3.89	-6.24	-9.22	-14.90	-15.31	-	-	-26.55	-
	[15-45[-80.40	-65.27	-51.44	-35.85	-27.43	-20.24	-17.64	-14.14	-10.12	-13.68	-14.08	-4.95	14.70	14.77	-	-	-
	[45-75[-109.19	-99.37	-80.74	-61.30	-41.02	-32.56	-27.99	-19.54	-15.93	-20.95	-25.26	-5.01	-0.82	-	-	-	-
	[75-105[-47.32	-67.64	-60.77	-60.55	-42.17	-32.47	-29.02	-25.52	-19.35	-17.74	-10.89	-	-	-	-	-	-
	[105-135[11.44	39.92	27.80	10.45	10.94	4.94	-1.76	-3.29	-3.81	-8.90	-14.48	34.06	-	-	-	-	-
	[135-165[33.66	63.31	62.31	58.98	51.92	44.28	36.74	30.72	31.17	37.16	43.85	54.01	37.40	-	-	-	-
	[165-195[84.57	80.26	71.63	65.75	59.31	54.49	48.30	44.34	39.98	37.81	33.04	31.96	30.55	25.92	22.37	29.82	-
	[195-225[85.03	71.37	64.47	55.12	47.83	41.00	35.86	31.45	27.73	25.79	23.40	19.39	19.43	19.99	1.05	24.53	-
	[225-255[63.57	51.29	44.32	39.84	33.68	27.57	23.35	21.35	19.29	17.55	15.32	15.13	10.44	9.53	4.77	-	-
	[255-285[37.32	27.99	24.33	21.94	17.17	12.86	9.56	8.42	7.09	5.66	5.35	5.50	1.77	-2.14	0.83	2.71	-1.15
	[285-315[3.19	9.31	9.27	7.08	4.66	2.79	1.61	-1.41	-4.07	-6.22	-5.02	-7.57	-7.62	-15.45	-17.19	-	-
	[315-345[-17.92	-12.16	-4.94	-1.81	-1.83	-1.41	-2.36	-2.24	-4.84	-8.41	-12.33	-18.37	-10.75	-1.09	-7.00	-15.33	-

Figure 4.25 Probability distribution of wind-wave misalignment vs. WS_{10} and WD_{10} at N2

Table 4.18 Probability distribution table of wind-wave misalignment vs. WS_{10} and WD_{10} at N2

N2 (5.580929°W; 58.843280°N; d=83.0mMSL)
 CFSR WD_{10} , SW_{NE} , MWD_{Total} (2001-01-01-2021-12-31; $\Delta t=1h$; $\bar{T}=2h$) by WD_{10}

		Misalignment (°)											
		[-195-165]	[-165-135]	[-135-105]	[-105-75]	[-75-45]	[-45-15]	[-15-15]	[15-45]	[45-75]	[75-105]	[105-135]	[135-165]
WD_{10} (°N-from)	[-15-15]	-	-	0.35	5.79	11.42	20.47	52.54	9.40	0.01	-	-	-
	[15-45]	0.01	0.92	7.25	10.12	15.05	32.67	33.73	0.24	-	-	-	0.01
	[45-75]	1.92	8.74	10.34	11.07	20.44	37.77	9.62	0.03	-	-	0.01	0.05
	[75-105]	12.59	10.17	9.33	11.64	17.53	22.83	11.46	0.27	0.14	0.10	0.25	3.70
	[105-135]	8.90	6.11	6.91	6.34	6.88	18.32	12.36	2.65	1.88	2.90	9.83	16.91
	[135-165]	5.50	4.94	2.98	1.88	2.26	4.75	7.61	7.16	11.51	20.08	23.46	7.88
	[165-195]	3.74	1.23	0.79	0.65	0.39	0.78	1.99	19.92	35.77	23.53	6.60	4.61
	[195-225]	0.58	0.18	0.16	0.09	0.08	0.23	6.20	53.22	28.36	5.80	3.14	1.96
	[225-255]	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.28	22.12	59.68	11.11	3.99	2.13	0.41
	[255-285]	0.01	-	0.02	0.01	0.04	2.63	58.98	27.22	7.21	3.53	0.31	0.04
	[285-315]	-	-	-	0.01	1.22	21.48	47.90	19.99	8.32	1.05	0.04	-
	[315-345]	-	-	-	0.63	10.02	23.40	36.61	26.74	2.59	0.01	-	-

4.4.6 Workability Tables/ Weather window

Weather windows of H_{m0} were calculated for duration of 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60 and 72 hours and for significant wave height thresholds of 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75, 2.00, 2.25, 2.50, 2.75, 3.00, 3.25, 3.50, 3.75 and 4.00 m. Analyses were performed for the 20-, 50- and 80-percentiles values.

The results of the analyses at N2 are presented in graphical and tabular format and they illustrate the percentage of time during which a given condition can be expected to occur in each month. The vertical bars in the plot indicate the standard deviation for each threshold, which are also designated by the numbers in the parentheses. A more in-depth explanation of the weather

windows can be found in the DHI Persistence (Weather Windows) document in Appendix A.

As an example, Figure 4.26 and Table 4.19 present the weather window of H_{m0} for a window of 2 hours and 50-percentile. The weather window of H_{m0} is lower during winter (November to January) and higher during summer (May to July).

All the performed weather windows of H_{m0} can be found in the digital delivery folder.

Figure 4.26 Persistence (weather-window) of H_{m0} at N2 for several thresholds. Window of 2 hours (50-percentile)

Table 4.19 Frequency table of persistence (weather-window) of H_{m0} at N2 for several thresholds. Window duration of 2 hours (50-percentile)

H_{m0} [m]	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
< 0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
< 0.75	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	1.6	0.6	0	0	0	0
< 1	0	0	0	0.7	7.9	12.2	13.4	13.1	2	0.7	0	0
< 1.25	0	0	0.5	7.2	20.3	32.6	36.4	28.1	9.6	7	0	0.9
< 1.5	0	0.6	5.2	16.6	37.2	52.4	59.6	51	20.8	11.8	1.7	3.4
< 1.75	0.5	3.3	9.6	26.7	48.3	68.5	73.4	64.4	34.6	22.1	5.2	6.3
< 2	4	7	17.6	37.7	63	79.9	83.7	76	47.7	32.2	11.2	9.9
< 2.25	11.8	13.1	27.9	51.7	74.9	87.2	89.5	81.7	55.3	41.9	19.4	15.7
< 2.5	19	20.6	36.4	62.8	82.1	91.2	94	87.2	63.5	53.8	27.1	22.8
< 2.75	28.8	28.7	43.7	69.4	86.2	93.4	96.1	90.7	70.3	61.2	38.8	29.1
< 3	35	40	49.4	79.9	90.9	95.9	96.8	93.1	76	71	47	36.8
< 3.25	43.4	51.2	56.4	83.8	95.2	98	97.4	94.8	81.9	76.7	57.5	45.3
< 3.5	50.9	58.9	63.4	87	97	99.4	98.7	96.6	86.3	81.6	64.1	52.3
< 3.75	56.7	67.3	70.8	89	97.5	99.9	99.6	97.6	89.7	84.5	68.4	58.4
< 4	62	72.2	75.5	92	98.5	100	100	98.1	91	88.5	73.5	65.8

5 Extreme Conditions

This section presents the extreme conditions analyses, which were performed at the analysis point N2. The analyses were based on the CFSR (winds), HD_{UKNS} (water levels and currents) and SW_{NE} forced with CFSR (waves) model datasets.

The period considered for extreme conditions analyses was 20 years from 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

The directional analyses were conducted for 12 directional bins of 30 degrees centered at 0°N, 30°N, etc. The directional values are not scaled for the analysis.

The extreme conditions analyses were conducted for the wind speed (10 mMSL and 150 mMSL), water levels (high and low), waves and currents.

All the performed extreme analyses results can be found in the digital delivery.

5.1 Winds

Estimates of the extreme wind speeds WS₁₀ and WS₁₅₀ were established based on the data from the CFSR model for the 20-year period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

The extreme wind speeds presented in this section correspond to 2-hour average. The common temporal conversion factors of extreme wind speed is presented in Table 5.1

Table 5.1 Common temporal conversion factors of extreme wind speed (2 h is the averaging period of CFSR hindcast wind data).

Reference	Remark	3-h	2-h	1-h	10-min	1-min	3-s
DNV (DNV, 2021)	20m/s, 10m height	-	-	1.00	1.08	1.19	1.32
	30m/s, 10m height	-	-	1.00	1.10	1.23	1.40
ISO (ISO, 2015) (Frøya)	40m/s, 10m height	-	-	1.00	1.12	1.27	1.47
	40m/s, 30m height	-	-	1.00	1.09	1.22	1.37
IEC ^{1,3} (IEC, 2019)	All speeds/heights	0.95	0.97	1.00	1.05	-	-
CEM (CEM, 2008)	All speeds/heights	0.93	0.95	1.00	1.05	1.24	1.51
WMO ² (WMO, 2010)	All speeds/heights	-	-	1.00	1.03	1.11	1.30

¹ Converted from being relative to the 10-min value to being relative to the 1-h value.

² WMO is recommended specifically for tropical cyclones.

³ The 2 h factor was obtained by interpolating between 3 h and 1 h.

5.1.1 Extreme Wind Speeds

The sensitivity test for the extreme value analyses were run for the 20 years of data for wind speed at 10 mMSL at N2 using different distribution fits for 100-year extreme as depicted in Figure 5.1. The considered distributions for wind conditions include truncated Weibull, 2-parameter Weibull, and exponential distributions with both Least Squares (LS) and Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimations for average annual peak (AAP) of 0.5 to 5, and Gumbel distribution with both LS and ML estimations for annual maximum peak (AMP) of 1.

The Gumbel distribution using the ML estimation with AMP of 1 lies in the higher end of the estimates (more conservative). This distribution is chosen for the extreme analysis herein for pre-FEED study, but other distributions should be considered at later design stages.

The 1, 50 and 100-year extreme for the omni-directional WS_{10} was performed and presented in Figure 5.2.

Additionally, the 1, 50 and 100-year directional extreme for WS_{10} is presented in Figure 5.3. A table with the extreme values at 10 mMSL are shown in Table 5.2. The respective results for WS_{150} can be found in the digital delivery.

Moreover, the 1, 50 and 100-year directional and omni extreme values for wind speed at 150 mMSL (hub height) were also estimated using the shear exponent of 0.11 based on (IEC, International Standard. Wind energy generation systems - Par 1: Design requirements, 2019) for extreme conditions instead of 0.14 (Section 4.1), which can be found in Table 5.3. Here, a disclaimer should be raised on the need for a proper wind characterisation using in-situ observations before a more detailed analysis can be undertaken.

Figure 5.1 Sensitivity tests of 100-year WS_{10} at N2 using different distributions

Figure 5.2 Estimate of extreme omni-directional WS₁₀ at analysis point N2 for 1, 50 and 100-year extreme
Gumbel distribution fitted to WS₁₀ data along with the extreme values at different return period [years]. 2.5% and 97.5% confidence bounds are shown with dashed blue line.

Figure 5.3 Estimate of directional extreme WS₁₀ at analysis point N2 [Gumbel distribution fitted to WS₁₀ data along with the extreme values at different return period [years]].

Table 5.2 Estimate of directional and omni extreme WS₁₀ at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/WS10	1	50	100
0	20.6	31.2	33.1
30	18.8	26.8	28.2
60	16.8	23.9	25.2
90	16.6	25.1	26.6
120	18.6	27.0	28.5
150	19.6	25.6	26.7
180	22.6	31.3	32.8
210	25.0	31.8	33.0
240	24.5	32.3	33.7
270	23.9	33.8	35.6
300	22.0	31.5	33.2
330	19.9	31.0	33.0
Omni	27	36.4	38

Table 5.3 Estimate of directional and omni extreme WS₁₅₀ at analysis point N2 using a wind shear exponent of 0.11. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/WS150	1	50	100
0	27.7	42.0	44.6
30	25.3	36.1	38.0
60	22.6	32.2	33.9
90	22.4	33.8	35.8
120	25.1	36.4	38.4
150	26.4	34.5	36.0
180	30.4	42.2	44.2
210	33.7	42.8	44.5
240	33.0	43.5	45.4
270	32.2	45.5	48.0
300	29.6	42.4	44.7
330	26.8	41.8	44.5
Omni	36.4	49.0	51.2

5.2 Water Levels

Estimates of the extreme water levels for total high-water level (WL) and total low-water level (LWL) was established based on the data from the HD_{UKNS} model for the 20-year period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

5.2.1 Extreme Water Levels

Only the total water level is used for extreme value estimation, i.e. the tidal and residual components are not calculated explicitly. The sensitivity test for the extreme value analyses were run for the 20 years of data for water levels at N2 using different distribution fits for 100-year extreme as depicted in Figure 5.4. The considered distributions are the same as for wind speed (c.f. Section 5.1).

Testing against different candidate distributions has shown several distributions may be a suitable fit, of which 2-p Weibull distribution using the LS estimation with AAP of 3 seemed to perform the best fit.

1, 50 and 100-year extreme for the omni-directional WL and LWL extremes were performed and presented in Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6.

Tables with extreme values for WL and LWL based on central estimate is presented in Table 5.4.

Figure 5.4 Sensitivity tests of 100-year water level at N2 using different distributions

Figure 5.5 Estimate of extreme omnidirectional total WL at analysis point N2 for 1, 50 and 100-year extreme.
2-p Weibull distribution fitted to WL data along with the extreme values at different return period [years]. 2.5% and 97.5% confidence bounds are shown with dashed blue line.

Figure 5.6 Estimate of extreme omnidirectional total LWL at analysis point N2 for 1, 50 and 100-year extreme
2-p Weibull distribution fitted to WL data along with the extreme values at different return period [years]. 2.5% and 97.5% confidence bounds are shown with dashed blue line.

Table 5.4 Extreme estimates of WL and LWL with return periods of 1, 50 and 100 years at N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

Water level (central est.)	1	50	100
WL	2.3	2.7	2.8
LWL	-2.2	-2.5	-2.5

5.3 Currents

Estimates of the extreme total depth-averaged current was established based on the data from the HD_{UKNS} model for the 20-year period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

5.3.1 Extreme Current Speeds

As for water levels, only the total depth-averaged current speed (CS) is used for extreme value estimation, i.e. the tidal and residual components are not calculated explicitly. The sensitivity test for the extreme value analyses were run for the 20 years of data for current speed at N2 using different distribution fits for 100-year extreme as depicted in Figure 5.7. The considered distributions are the same as for wind speed (c.f. Section 5.1).

Testing against different candidate distributions has shown several distributions may be a suitable fit, of which 2-p Weibull distribution using the LS estimation with AAP of 2 seemed to perform the best fit.

1, 50 and 100-year extreme for the omni-directional current speed extremes were performed and presented in Figure 5.8.

Additionally, the 1, 50 and 100-year directional extreme for current speed is presented in Figure 5.9, and the corresponding extreme table are shown in Table 5.5.

Figure 5.7 Sensitivity tests of 100-year CS at N2 using different distributions

Figure 5.8 Estimate of extreme omni-directional CS at analysis point N2 for 1, 50 and 100-year extreme
 2-p Weibull distribution fitted to CS data along with the extreme values at different return period [years]. 2.5% and 97.5% confidence bounds are shown with dashed blue line.

Figure 5.9 Estimate of directional extreme CS at analysis point N2
2-p Weibull distribution fitted to CS data along with the extreme values at different return period [years].

Table 5.5 Estimate of directional and omni extreme CS at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31.

TR/CS	1	50	100
0	0.18	0.27	0.28
30	0.33	0.48	0.50
60	0.75	1.05	1.10
90	0.65	0.81	0.84
120	0.31	0.45	0.47
150	0.22	0.28	0.29
180	0.23	0.27	0.28
210	0.34	0.45	0.47
240	0.60	0.75	0.77
270	0.58	0.72	0.74
300	0.25	0.33	0.34
330	0.17	0.22	0.23
Omni	0.75	1.05	1.10

5.4 Waves

Estimates of the extreme waves were established based on the data from the SW_{NE} forced with CFSR model for the 20-year period 2001-01-01 to 2021-12-31.

5.4.1 Extreme Significant Wave Height (H_{m0})

The sensitivity test for the extreme value analyses were run for the 20 years of data for significant wave height at N2 using different distribution fits for 100-year extreme as depicted in Figure 5.10. The considered distributions are the same as for wind speed (c.f. Section 5.1).

Testing against different candidate distributions has shown that 2-p Weibull distribution using the LS estimation with AAP of 3 fits the extreme events fits significant wave height well.

1, 50 and 100-year extreme for the omni-directional significant wave height extremes were performed and presented in Figure 5.11.

Additionally, the 1, 50 and 100-year directional extreme for significant wave height is presented in Figure 5.12, and corresponding extreme tables are found in Table 5.6.

Figure 5.10 Sensitivity tests of 100-year H_{m0} at N2 using different distributions

Figure 5.11 Estimate of extreme omni-directional H_{m0} at analysis point N2 for 1, 50 and 100-year extreme
2-p Weibull distribution fitted to H_{m0} data along with the extreme values at different return period [years]. 2.5% and 97.5% confidence bounds are shown with dashed blue line.

Figure 5.12 Estimate of directional extreme H_{m0} at analysis point N2 [2-p Weibull distribution fitted to H_{m0} data along with the extreme values at different return period [years]].

Table 5.6 Estimate of directional and omni extreme H_{m0} at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/Hm0	1	50	100
0	7.2	12.1	12.9
30	5.2	9.2	9.8
60	3.8	8.5	9.5
90	3.7	6.6	7.1
120	3.4	5.3	5.7
150	3.3	6.0	6.5
180	3.6	5.7	6.1
210	6.6	9.6	10.1
240	8.6	12.2	12.7
270	10.4	14.9	15.6
300	8.8	14.0	14.8
330	7.3	13.2	14.2
Omni	10.8	15.2	15.9

5.4.2 Associated T_p to extreme H_{m0}

The associated T_p to the extreme H_{m0} is found by using the relationship between H_{m0} vs T_p under normal conditions for the 0.05, 0.50 and 0.95 quantiles (see Figure 4.22 for the omni-directional relation and digital delivery for directional relation).

The calculated omni and directional $T_{p,0.05}$, $T_{p,0.50}$ and $T_{p,0.95}$ can be found in Table 5.7 to Table 5.9. Due to few waves for the 150-degree direction the relationship between T_p and H_{m0} for the 180-degree direction is used to calculate the extreme T_p .

Table 5.7 Estimate of associated directional and omni extreme T_p for 0.05 (5%) quantile at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/ $T_{p_0.05}$	1	50	100
0	12.28	14.40	14.68
30	10.15	11.87	12.08
60	8.16	10.83	11.27
90	7.82	9.99	10.30
120	6.96	7.84	8.00
150	7.10	8.15	8.30
180	7.24	8.05	8.18
210	9.21	10.61	10.82
240	11.29	12.08	12.17
270	14.24	16.34	16.62
300	13.45	14.89	15.07
330	12.09	13.93	14.17
Omni	13.79	15.72	16.00

Table 5.8 Estimate of associated directional and omni extreme T_p for 0.50 (50%) quantile at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/ $T_{p_0.50}$	1	50	100
0	13.41	15.72	16.03
30	11.24	13.15	13.38
60	9.98	13.25	13.78
90	8.25	10.54	10.87
120	7.75	8.74	8.92
150	10.93	12.55	12.78
180	11.15	12.40	12.60
210	9.76	11.24	11.46
240	14.39	15.39	15.51
270	17.06	19.57	19.91
300	14.70	16.27	16.47
330	13.62	15.68	15.96
Omni	16.94	19.31	19.65

Table 5.9 Estimate of associated directional and omni extreme T_p for 0.95 (95%) quantile at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/ $T_p_{0.95}$	1	50	100
0	14.96	17.54	17.88
30	13.13	15.36	15.63
60	13.48	17.90	18.61
90	12.28	15.68	16.17
120	18.47	20.83	21.24
150	15.59	17.89	18.23
180	15.90	17.68	17.96
210	12.34	14.21	14.49
240	18.30	19.58	19.73
270	18.95	21.74	22.12
300	16.31	18.05	18.27
330	15.13	17.43	17.73
Omni	19.21	21.90	22.29

5.4.3 Extreme maximum individual wave height (H_{max})

The 1, 50 and 100-year directional extreme for maximum wave height (H_{max}) using the Forristall short-term wave height distribution is presented in Figure 5.13 and corresponding extreme table are found in Table 5.10.

Figure 5.13 Estimate of directional extreme H_{max} at analysis point N2
2-p Weibull distribution fitted to H_{max} data along with the extreme values at different return period [years].

Table 5.10 Estimate of directional and omni extreme H_{max} at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/Hmax	1	50	100
0	12.7	22	23.7
30	9.3	16.5	17.8
60	6.5	15.4	17.1
90	6.8	12	12.8
120	5.8	9.5	10.1
150	5.3	9.7	10.4
180	6	10.2	10.9
210	11.2	17.4	18.4
240	15	21.8	22.9
270	18.6	27.7	29.2
300	15.5	24.5	26
330	12.7	23.4	25.3
Omni	19.5	27.9	29.3

5.4.4 Associated TH_{max} to extreme H_{max}

The associated TH_{max} to the extreme H_{max} was estimated following the DNV RP-C205 standards using the relationship between T_p and H_{m0} :

$$TH_{max} = 2.94 H_{max}^{0.5}$$

The estimated omni-directional values for TH_{max} are summarised in Table 5.11.

Table 5.11 Estimate of omni-directional associated TH_{max} to the extreme H_{max} at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31

TR/ TH_{max}	1	50	100
0	10.5	13.8	14.3
30	9.0	11.9	12.4
60	7.5	11.5	12.2
90	7.7	10.2	10.5
120	7.1	9.1	9.3
150	6.8	9.2	9.5
180	7.2	9.4	9.7
210	9.8	12.3	12.6
240	11.4	13.7	14.1
270	12.7	15.5	15.9
300	11.6	14.6	15.0
330	10.5	14.2	14.8
Omni	13.0	15.5	15.9

5.4.5 Extreme maximum crest height (C_{max})

The 1, 50 and 100-year directional extreme for maximum wave height (C_{max}) using the Forristall short-term wave crest distribution is presented in Figure 5.14 and corresponding extreme table are found in Table 5.12.

Figure 5.14 Estimate of directional extreme C_{max} at analysis point N2
2-p Weibull distribution fitted to C_{max} data along with the extreme values at different return period [years].

Table 5.12 Estimate of directional and omni extreme C_{max} at analysis point N2. Data from 2001-01-01 – 2021-12-31.

TR/Cmax	1	50	100
0	8.3	13.8	14.8
30	6.4	10.4	11
60	4.9	10.8	12
90	5.1	7.8	8.2
120	4.5	7	7.3
150	4	6.7	7.1
180	4.5	7.6	8.1
210	7.9	12.6	13.5
240	10.2	14.2	14.8
270	12.3	18.2	19.2
300	10.1	16.1	17.2
330	8.3	14.3	15.4
Omni	12.8	18.4	19.4

5.5 Join Probability Analysis

Joint probability analyses (JPA) of the total significant wave height and wind speed at 10 mMSL and 150 mMSL were conducted. The JPA for total H_{m0} associated with extreme omni-directional WS_{10} is presented and discussed in this report (JPA for WS_{150} can be found in digital delivery folder). The performed extreme analyses follows the method described in Appendix B.

The omni-directional JPA at N2 are provided in Figure 5.15 and the corresponding H_{m0} associated to the extreme wind values are presented in Table 5.13.

Figure 5.15 Joint probability of H_{m0} associated with extreme omni-directional WS_{10} at N2.

Table 5.13 Total H_{m0} associated with extreme omni-directional WS_{10} for return periods 1, 50 and 100 years (0.05, 0.50 and 0.95 quantiles) at N2

Associated parameter	WS_{10} [m/s]	$H_{m0,0.05}$	$H_{m0,0.50}$	$H_{m0,0.95}$
H_{m0} 1yr [m]	27.0	6.2	8.7	12.1
H_{m0} 50yr [m]	36.4	10.0	12.6	16.9
H_{m0} 100yr [m]	38.0	10.5	13.2	17.7

6 References

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Appendix A DHI Persistence Model (Weather Windows)

See next pages

DHI Persistence (Weather Windows)

Contents

1 **DHI Persistence (Weather Windows)** 2

Revisions

Date	Description	Initials
2021-08-13	Version 1.0.	PDG

Nomenclature

Abbreviation	Explanation
H_{m0}	Zeroth moment significant wave height [m]
P	Percentile

1 DHI Persistence (Weather Windows)

The persistence (also known as weather window and/or downtime) is defined as a continued occurrence of a given minimum duration which a given parameter's value remains higher or lower than a given threshold. A weather window is defined as a continued occurrence during which the given conditions (duration and threshold) are fulfilled, while downtime is defined as the remainder periods (i.e., all periods that are not weather windows). The sum of weather windows and downtime for any given condition thus equals 100% of the time.

The durations may be defined as either 'Overlapping' or 'Non-overlapping'. Overlapping duration refers to persistence that includes the fraction of duration at the end of each weather window, while non-overlapping duration includes whole number of windows only. Overlapping duration thus results in higher occurrence of weather windows (and lower occurrence of downtime). The thresholds may be defined as being either above or below a given value depending on what is critical for the parameter in question. The default is the 'Overlapping' method.

An illustration of persistence over 1 month (31 days) is presented in Figure 1.1. As an example, the persistence for an overlapping duration ≥ 1 day (24 hours) and a threshold $H_{m0} < 4.0\text{m}$ yields weather windows of 93.2% of the time (28.9 days) and corresponding downtime of 6.8% (2.1 days) during that month.

Figure 1.1 Example of persistence over one month

The uncertainty related to yearly variations may be estimated by calculating the persistence statistics for each available year and subsequently derive the mean, standard deviation, and/or any given certainty percentile. A percentile (P) above 50% in this case refers to a more conservative estimate (i.e., less weather windows and more downtime) and vice versa.

The persistence statistics are presented in graphical and tabular format as a percentage of time during each considered interval (e.g., month). Windows stretching through more than one interval contributes with a corresponding fraction of the window to each of the intervals.

Appendix B DHI Extreme Value Analysis (EVA)

See next pages

DHI Extreme Value Analysis (EVA)

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Revisions

Date	Description	Initials
2021-08-13	Version 1.0.	PDG

Nomenclature

Abbreviation	Explanation
C	Individual crest level [m]
C_{max}	Maximum (highest) individual crest level [m]
C_{mp}	Most probable maximum individual crest level in a storm event [m]
H_{m0}	Zerth moment significant wave height [m]
H	Individual (trough-crest) wave height [m]
H_{max}	Maximum (highest) individual (trough-crest) wave height [m]
H_{mp}	Most probable maximum individual wave height in a storm event [m]
T_R	Return period [years]

1 DHI Extreme Value Analysis (EVA)

This document describes the DHI extreme value analysis (EVA).

1.1 Summary of approach

Extreme values with conditioned long return periods are estimated by fitting a probability distribution to historical data. Several distributions, data selection and fitting techniques are available for estimation of extremes, and the estimated extremes are often rather sensitive to the choice of method. However, it is not possible to choose a preferred method only on its superior theoretical support or widespread acceptance within the industry. Hence, it is common practice to test several approaches and make the final decision based on goodness of fit.

The typical extreme value analyses involved the following steps:

1. Extraction of independent identically-distributed events by requiring that events are separated by at least 36 hours (or similar), and that the value between events had dropped to below 70% (or similar) of the minor of two consecutive events. The extraction is conducted individually for omni and directional/seasonal subsets respectively.
2. Fitting of extreme value distribution to the extracted events, individually for omni and directional/seasonal subsets. Distribution parameters are estimated either by maximum likelihood or least-square methods. The following analysis approaches are used (see Section 1.2 for details):
 - Fitting the Gumbel distribution to annual maxima.
 - Fitting a distribution to all events above a certain threshold (the Peak-Over-Threshold method). The distribution type can be exponential, truncated Weibull or 2-parameter Weibull to excess.
3. Constraining of subseries to ensure consistency with the omni/all-year distribution; see Section 1.4 for details.
4. Bootstrapping to estimate the uncertainty due to sampling error; see Section 1.6 for details.
5. Values of other parameters conditioned on extremes of one variable are estimated using the methodology proposed in [1] (Heffernan & Tawn).

Figure 1.1 shows an example of EVA based on 38 years of hindcast data and a Gumbel distribution fitted to the annual maxima using max. likelihood.

Figure 1.1 Example of traditional extreme value analysis of H_{m0} .

A Gumbel distribution fitted to the annual maxima using maximum likelihood.

1.2 Long-term distributions

The following probability distributions are often used in connection with extreme value estimation:

- 2-parameter Weibull distribution
- Truncated Weibull distribution

- Exponential distribution
- Gumbel distribution

The 2-parameter Weibull distribution is given by:

$$P(X < x) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right) \quad (1.1)$$

with distribution parameters α (shape) and β (scale). The 2-parameter Weibull distribution used in connection with Peak-Over-Threshold (POT) analysis is fitted to the excess of data above the threshold, i.e., the threshold value is subtracted from data prior to fitting.

The 2-parameter *truncated* Weibull distribution is given by:

$$P(X < x) = 1 - \frac{1}{P_0} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right) \quad (1.2)$$

with distribution parameters α (shape) and β (scale) and the exceedance probability, P_0 , at the threshold level, γ , given by:

$$P_0 = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\gamma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right) \quad (1.3)$$

The 2-parameter truncated Weibull distribution is used in connection with Peak-Over-Threshold analysis, and as opposed to the non-truncated 2-p Weibull, it is fitted directly to data, i.e., the threshold value is **not** subtracted from data prior to fitting.

The exponential distribution is given by:

$$P(X < x) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x - \mu}{\beta}\right)\right), \quad x \geq \mu \quad (1.4)$$

with distribution parameters β (scale) and μ (location). Finally, the Gumbel distribution is given by:

$$P(X < x) = \exp\left(-\exp\left(\frac{\mu - x}{\beta}\right)\right) \quad (1.5)$$

with distribution parameters β (scale) and μ (location).

1.3 Individual wave and crest height

Short-term distributions

The short-term distributions of individual wave heights and crests conditional on H_{m0} are assumed to follow the distributions proposed by Forristall, (Forristall G. Z., 1978) and (Forristall G. Z., 2000). The Forristall wave height distribution is based on Gulf of Mexico measurements, but experience from the North Sea has shown that these distributions may have a more general applicability. The Forristall wave and crest height distributions are given by:

$$P(X > x | H_{m0}) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha H_{m0}}\right)^\beta\right) \quad (1.6)$$

where the distribution parameters, α and β , are as follows:

Forristall wave height: $\alpha = 0.681$ $\beta = 2.126$

Forristall crest height (3D): $\alpha = 0.3536 + 0.2568 \cdot S_1 + 0.0800 \cdot U_r$

$\beta = 2 - 1.7912 \cdot S_1 - 0.5302 \cdot U_r + 0.284 \cdot U_r^2$

$$S_1 = \frac{2\pi}{g} \frac{H_{m0}}{T_{01}^2} \quad \text{and} \quad U_r = \frac{H \cdot L^2}{d^3}$$

For this type of distribution, the distribution of the extremes of a given number of events, N , (waves or crests) converges towards the Gumbel distribution conditional on the most probable value of the extreme event, H_{mp} (or C_{mp} for crests):

$$P(h_{\max} | H_{mp}) = \exp \left(- \exp \left(- \ln N \left(\left(\frac{h_{\max}}{H_{mp}} \right)^\beta - 1 \right) \right) \right) \quad (1.7)$$

1.3.1 Individual waves (modes)

The extreme individual wave and crest heights are derived using the storm mode approach, (Tromans, P.S. and Vanderschuren, L., 1995). The storm modes, or most probable values of the maximum wave or crest in the storm (H_{mp} or C_{mp}), are obtained by integrating the short-term distribution of wave heights conditional on H_{m0} over the entire number of sea states making up the storm. In practice, this is done by following these steps:

1. Storms are identified by peak extraction from the time series of significant wave height. Individual storms are taken as portions of the time series with H_{m0} above 0.7 times the storm peak, H_{m0} .
2. The wave (or crest) height distribution is calculated for each sea state above the threshold in each individual storm. The short-term distribution of H (or C) conditional on H_{m0} , $P(h|H_{m0})$, is assumed to follow the empirical distributions by Forristall (see Section 1.3). The wave height probability distribution is then given by the following product over the n sea states making up the storm:

$$P(H_{\max} < h) = \prod_{j=1}^{n_{\text{sestates}}} P(h | H_{m0,j})^{N_{\text{waves},j}} \quad (1.8)$$

with the number of waves in each sea state, N_{waves} , being estimated by deriving the mean zero-crossing period of the sea state. The most probable maximum wave height (or mode), H_{mp} , of the storm is given by:

$$P(H_{\max} < h) = \frac{1}{e} \quad (1.9)$$

This produces a database of historical storms each characterised by its most probable maximum individual wave height which is used for further extreme value analysis.

1.3.2 Convolution of short-term variability with long-term storm density

The long-term distribution of individual waves and crests is found by convolution of the long-term distribution of the modes (subscript $_{mp}$ for most probable value) with the distribution of the maximum conditional on the mode given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(H_{\max}) &= \int_0^{\infty} P(h_{\max} | H_{mp}) \cdot p(H_{mp}) dH_{mp} \\
 &= \int_0^{\infty} \exp\left(-\exp\left(-\ln N \left(\left(\frac{h}{H_{mp}}\right)^{\beta} - 1\right)\right)\right) \cdot p(H_{mp}) dH_{mp}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.10}$$

The value of N , which goes into this equation, is determined by defining equivalent storm properties for each individual storm. The equivalent storms have constant H_{m0} and a duration such that their probability density function of H_{\max} or C_{\max} matches that of the actual storm. The density functions of the maximum wave in the equivalent storms are given by:

$$p(H_{\max} | H_{m0,eq}, N_{eq}) = \frac{d}{dH} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{H_{\max}}{\alpha \cdot H_{m0,eq}}\right)^{\beta}\right) \right]^{N_{eq}} \tag{1.11}$$

The β parameter in eq. (1.10) comes from the short-term distribution of individual crests, eq. ((1.6), and is a function of wave height and wave period. Based on previous studies, it has been assessed that the maximum crest heights are not sensitive to β_C for a constant value of 1.88 and hence, it is decided to apply $\beta_C = 1.88$. The number of waves in a storm, N , was conservatively calculated from a linear fit to the modes minus one standard deviation.

1.4 Subset extremes

Estimates of subset (e.g., directional, and monthly) extremes are required for several parameters. To establish these extremes, it is common practice to fit extreme value distributions to data sampled from the population (i.e., the model database) that fulfils the specific requirement e.g., to direction, i.e., the extremes from each direction are extracted and distributions fitted to each set of directional data in turn. By sampling an often relatively small number of values from the data set, each of these directional distributions is subject to uncertainty due to sampling error. This will often lead to the directional distributions being inconsistent with the omnidirectional distribution fitted to the maxima of the entire (omnidirectional) data set. Consistency between directional and omnidirectional distributions is ensured by requiring that the product of the n directional annual non-exceedance probabilities equals the omnidirectional, i.e.:

$$\prod_{i=1}^n F_i(x, \hat{\theta}_i)^{N_i} = F_{omni}(x, \hat{\theta}_{omni})^{N_{omni}} \tag{1.12}$$

where N_i is the number of sea states or events for the i 'th direction and $\hat{\theta}_i$, the estimated distribution parameter. This is ensured by estimating the distribution parameters for the individual distributions and then minimising the deviation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta = \sum_{x_j} \left[-\ln\left(-N_{omni} \ln F_{omni}(x, \hat{\theta}_{omni})\right) \right. \\
 \left. + \ln\left(-\sum_{i=1}^n N_i \ln F_i(x_j, \hat{\theta}_i)\right) \right]^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.13}$$

Here x_j are extreme values of the parameter for which the optimisation is carried out, i.e., the product of the directional non-exceedance probabilities is forced to match the omnidirectional for these values of the parameter in question.

The directional extremes presented in this report are given without scaling, that is, a T_{yr} event from direction i will be exceeded once every T years on the average. The same applies for monthly extremes. A T_{yr} monthly event corresponds to the event that is exceeded once (in that month) every T years, which is the same as saying that it is exceeded once every $T/12$ years (on average) of the climate for that month.

1.4.1 Optimised directional extremes

The directional extremes are derived from fits to each subseries data set meaning that a T_R year event from each direction will be exceeded once every T_R years on average. Having e.g., 12 directions, this means that **one** of the directions will be exceeded once every $T_R/12$ years on average. A 100-year event would thus be exceeded once every $100/12 = 8\frac{1}{3}$ years (on average) from **one** of the directions.

For design application, it is often required that the summed (overall) return period (probability) is T_R years. A simple way of fulfilling this would be to take the return value corresponding to the return period T_R times the number of directions, i.e., in this case the $12 \times 100 = 1200$ -year event for each direction. However, this is often not optimal since it may lead to very high estimates for the strong sectors, while the weak sectors may still be insignificant.

Alternatively, an optimised set of directional extreme values may be produced for design purpose in addition to the individual values of directional extremes described above. The optimised values are derived by increasing (scaling) the individual T_R values of the directions to obtain a summed (overall) probability of T_R years while ensuring that the extreme values of the strong sector(s) become as close to the overall extreme value as possible. In practice, this is done by increasing the T_R of the weak directions more than that of the strong sectors but ensuring that the sum of the inverse directional T_R 's equals the inverse of the targeted return period, i.e.:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{T_{R,i}} = \frac{1}{T_{R,omni}} \quad (1.14)$$

where n is the number of directional sectors and $T_{R,omni}$ is the targeted overall return period.

1.5 Uncertainty assessment

The extreme values are estimated quantities and therefore all associated with uncertainty. The uncertainty arises from several sources:

Measurement/model uncertainty

The contents of the database for the extreme value analysis are associated with uncertainty. This type of uncertainty is preferably mitigated at the source – e.g., by correction of biased model data and removal of obvious outliers in data series. The model uncertainty can be quantified if simultaneous good quality measurements are available for a reasonably long overlapping period.

True extreme value distribution is unknown

The distribution of extremes is theoretically unknown for levels above the levels contained in the extreme value database. There is no justification for the assumption that a parametric extreme value distribution fitted to observed/modelled data can be extrapolated beyond the observed levels. However, it is common practice to do so, and this obviously is a source of uncertainty in the derived extreme value estimates. This uncertainty, increasing with decreasing occurrence probability of the event in question, is not quantifiable but the metocean expert may minimise it by using experience and knowledge when deciding on an appropriate extreme value analysis approach. Proper inclusion of other information than direct measurements and model results may also help to minimise this type of uncertainty.

Uncertainty due to sampling error

The number of observed/modelled extreme events is limited. This gives rise to sampling error which can be quantified by statistical methods such as Monte Carlo simulations or bootstrap resampling. The results of such an analysis are termed the confidence limits. The confidence limits (see Section 1.6) should **not** be mistaken for the total uncertainty in the extreme value estimate.

Settings of the analysis (judgement)

Any EVA involves the need to define the various settings of the analysis (threshold, distribution, and fitting method), which introduces subjectivity to the analysis. The sensitivity of these settings can be assessed by comparing the resulting extreme values, and the goodness of fit can, to some extent, be objectively assessed by statistical measures. However, standard practice typically includes manual inspection of the fitted distributions. Hence, the final settings, and thus results, relies on the experience and preference of the metocean expert conducting the analysis ('engineering judgement'). The tail of the distributions (the values of long the return periods) can be particularly sensitive to the settings of the analysis.

1.6 Confidence limits

The confidence limits of extreme estimates are established from a bootstrap analysis or a Monte Carlo simulation.

The bootstrap analysis estimates the uncertainty due to sampling error. The bootstrap consists of the following steps:

1. Construct a new set of extreme events by sampling randomly with replacement from the original data set of extremes
2. Carry out an extreme value analysis on the new set to estimate T-year events

An empirical distribution of the T-year event is obtained by looping steps 1 and 2 many times. The percentiles are read from the resulting distribution.

In the Monte Carlo simulation, the uncertainty is estimated by randomly generating many samples that have the same statistical distribution as the observed sample.

The Monte Carlo simulation can be summarised in the following steps:

1. Randomly generating a sample consisting of N data points, using the estimated parameters of the original distribution. If the event selection is based on a fixed number of events, N is set equal to the size of original data set of extremes. If the event selection is based on a fixed threshold, the sample size N is assumed to be Poisson-distributed.
2. From the generated sample, the parameters of the distribution are estimated, and the T-year return estimates are established.

Steps 1 and 2 are looped numerous times, whereby an empirical distribution of the T-year event is obtained. The quartiles are read from the resulting distribution.

1.7 Joint probability analyses (JPA)

Values of other parameters conditioned on extremes of one variable are estimated using the methodology proposed in [1] (Heffernan & Tawn). This method consists in modelling the marginal distribution of each variable separately. The variables are transformed from physical space, X, to standard Gumbel space by the relationship:

$$Y = \text{LN} \left(-\text{LN} \left(F(X, \hat{\theta}) \right) \right) \quad (1.15)$$

where $F(X, \hat{\theta})$ denotes the distribution function of the variable, X , with estimated parameters, $\hat{\theta}$. No restriction is given on the marginal model of the variables. A combination of the empirical distribution for the bulk of events and a parametric extreme value distribution function fitted to the extreme tail of data was adopted here. For parameters which may have both a positive and a negative extreme such as the water level conditioned on wave height, both the positive and the negative extreme tail are modelled parametrically.

The dependence structure of the two variables is modelled in standard Gumbel distribution space, conditioning one variable by the other. The model takes the form:

$$(Y_2|Y_1 = y_1) = ay_1 + y_1^b Z \quad (1.16)$$

with Y_1 being the conditioning variable and Y_2 the conditioned. The residual, Z , is assumed to converge to a normal distribution, G , with increasing y_1 . The parameters, \hat{a} and \hat{b} , are found from regression and the parameters, $\hat{\mu}$ and $\hat{\sigma}$, of the normal distribution, G , estimated from the residuals, Z :

$$Z = \frac{y_2 - a \cdot y_1}{y_1^b} \quad (1.17)$$

Figure 1.2 shows an example of the modelled dependence structure for H_{m0} and water level in standard Gumbel space. Figure 1.3 shows the same in physical space. The model is clearly capable of describing the positive association between wave heights and water level for this condition and appears also to capture the relatively large spreading.

The applied joint probability model is event-based. This means that independent events of the conditioning parameter are extracted from the model data. The combined inter-event time and inter-event level criterion described in Section 1.1 is applied to isolate independent events of the conditioning parameter. The conditioned parameter is extracted from the model time series at the point in time of the peak of the conditioning parameter. Time averaging of the conditioned parameter is often carried out prior to data extraction to reduce the influence of phases in the analysis (the fact that the water level may not peak at the same time as the peak wave height for instance).

Figure 1.2 Dependence structure of H_{m0} and water level transformed into standard Gumbel space.

Figure 1.3 Dependence structure of H_{m0} and water level in physical space

1.8 References

- [1] J. E. Heffernan and J. A. Tawn, "A conditional approach for multivariate extreme values," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 497-546, 2004.